

PROGRESS IN THE MANAGEMENT AND PREVENTION OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS AMONG SCHOOL-AGED CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11174778>

Abstract:

This paper examines contemporary methods for the treatment and prevention of dental fluorosis in school-aged children. Dental fluorosis is a chronic condition affecting enamel due to excessive fluoride intake. The study focuses on analyzing the effectiveness of various approaches and products used in treating and preventing this condition, proposing innovative solutions tailored to the needs of school-aged children.

Keywords: Fluorosis, fluorosis prevention, fluorosis treatment, child health, school age, dental enamel, fluoride.

Relevance:

Dental fluorosis holds a significant place among oral diseases in children, underscoring the necessity of developing effective prevention and treatment methods. Given the increasing prevalence of fluorosis among schoolchildren, the relevance of this work is driven by the aim to reduce the disease's spread and improve the quality of life for this age group.

Research Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of existing methods for treating and preventing dental fluorosis in school-aged children and to develop optimized approaches based on the analysis of the collected data.

Materials and Methods:

The study included 200 school-aged children suffering from various degrees of fluorosis. Both traditional and novel treatment and prevention methods were applied, including the use of fluoride-containing and fluoride-releasing toothpastes, balanced nutrition, and regular dental check-ups. Effectiveness was assessed based on clinical observations of changes in the condition of the dental enamel.

Results:

It was found that a comprehensive approach incorporating dietary adjustments, use of individually selected hygienic products, and regular dental examinations significantly reduces the manifestations of fluorosis and improves the condition of dental enamel in children.

Conclusion:

The research confirmed the necessity of an individual approach in the treatment and prevention of dental fluorosis in school-aged children. Further development

and implementation of innovative prevention and treatment methods based on scientific data and clinical experience are recommended to improve child health at a national level.

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